

Supplementary materials

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1 Complementary Football Features Glossary

Table 1 contains all the complementary football statistics under consideration in this work, with their respective description.

Table 1: Glossary of all considered complementary football features (measured on the previous drive). *Subtracting the punt or kickoff yardage from the return yardage.

Name	Description
<i>off.ST.yards.gained</i>	Yards gained by offense and special teams return
<i>ST.return.yards.net</i>	Net yards on a special teams return ¹
<i>pts.scored</i>	Points scored
<i>first.downs.gained</i>	Number of first downs gained
<i>third.downs.converted</i>	Number of third downs converted
<i>takeaway.nonscor</i>	Interception, fumble/on-side kick recovery that didn't result in an instant score
<i>turnover.nonscor</i>	On top of non-scoring takeaways, also includes missed field goals and turnover on downs
<i>punt.safety</i>	Punt or safety
<i>n.completions</i>	Number of completed passes
<i>n.incompletions</i>	Number of incomplete passes
<i>n.stuffed.runs</i>	Number of runs for ≤ 0 yards
<i>n.positive.runs</i>	Number of runs for > 0 yards
<i>n.negative.plays</i>	Number of plays for < 0 yards, incl. penalties
<i>n.sacks</i>	Number of sacks
<i>n.fumbles</i>	Number of fumbles (lost and recovered)

¹Subtracting the punt or kickoff yardage from the return yardage. Will be mostly negative.

2 Residual Diagnostics

Figure 1 illustrates preliminary residual diagnostics for the proportional odds fit discussed in the "Preliminary Diagnostics" section of the main paper, involving all complementary football features under consideration (see Table 1), applied to the 2016 season data. The patterns for both the residuals-vs-fitted and quantile-quantile plot are indicative of a proper fit, with no deviations from linearity of predictor effects on the cumulative log-odds. In particular, the residuals-vs-fitted plot shows a linear average residual trend pattern centered at 0 with only a light evidence of inconsistent variance, while the QQ-plot exhibits a nearly perfect correspondence between theoretical and practical quantiles.

Figure 1: Surrogate residuals-vs-fitted (left) and quantile-quantile (right) plots for the preliminary proportional cumulative odds model fit on 2016 season data, with all complementary football features included.

Figures 2 and 3 contain the binarized surrogate residual diagnostics for the selected models with non-proportional cumulative odds as described in the "Selection stability analysis" section of the main paper. Figure 2 corresponds to residuals-vs-fitted plots, while Figure 3 shows the QQ-plots. The residuals-vs-fitted plots for the 2016 season demonstrate a linear pattern with the trend line centered at 0 and the variance being moderately consistent, while the QQ-plots confirm the alignment of the data with the logistic distribution assumed by our model.

Figure 2: Binarized surrogate residuals-vs-fitted plots for the non-proportional cumulative odds model fit to 2016 season data. accounting for the most consistent complementary football features.

Figure 3: Binarized surrogate residuals quantile-quantile (QQ) plots for the non-proportional cumulative odds model fit to 2016 season data accounting for the most consistent complementary football features.

3 Defensive Ranking Shifts

Table 2 presents the defensive ranking shifts for points allowed per drive during the 2016 college football season as discussed in the "Ranking shifts" section of the main paper.

Table 2: Partial 2016 season rankings in points allowed per drive by team's defense, adjusted for strength of schedule, homefield factor, offense's non-scoring giveaways and yards gained. Shifts are relative to adjusting only for strength of schedule and homefield factor.

Team	Points Allowed (Per Drive)		Offense Statistics (Per Drive)	
	Val (Shift)	Rk (Shift)	Giveaways Rk (Val)	Yards Gained Rk (Val)
Alabama	0.39 (↑ 0.02)	1 (=0)	66 (0.107)	33 (41)
Ohio State	0.68 (↑ 0.03)	2 (=0)	1 (0.033)	53 (38)
Michigan	0.76 (↑ 0.06)	3 (=0)	5 (0.057)	29 (41)
LSU	0.84 (↓ 0.02)	4 (=0)	87 (0.120)	31 (41)
Florida	0.88 (↓ 0.03)	5 (=0)	71 (0.112)	111 (32)
Wisconsin	0.96 (↓ 0.01)	6 (=0)	80 (0.116)	81 (36)
Miami	1.03 (=0.00)	7 (=0)	7 (0.058)	100 (33)
BYU	1.11 (↓ 0.03)	8 (↑ 2)	93 (0.124)	51 (39)
Washington	1.13 (↑ 0.04)	9 (↓ 1)	25 (0.079)	49 (39)
Auburn	1.13 (↑ 0.04)	10 (↓ 1)	6 (0.058)	23 (42)
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Kansas	1.91 (↓ 0.19)	57 (↑ 19)	129 (0.207)	126 (28)
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Western Michigan	2.09 (↑ 0.16)	76 (↓ 18)	2 (0.041)	6 (47)
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